

THE ROLE OF THE LEARNING AND GAME ENVIRONMENT IN THE FORMATION OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS

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Annotation: The article considers a model of a learning-playing environment created according to the block principle with the aim of educating the emotional and volitional qualities of younger schoolchildren in physical education lessons.

Key words: educational-playing environment, block principle, junior schoolchildren, emotional-volitional properties.

Introduction. The results of psychological and pedagogical research indicate that primary school age is the initial stage in the formation of a personality as a subject of educational activity [3, 19]. At this age, the child for the first time is included in a socially significant activity, in a wide sphere of communication, intensifying the process of self-knowledge [4, 17].

Scientists note the need to study the subjectivity of a younger student in the context of his participation in educational activities [1, 2, 3]. When approaching the student's personality as a complex and integral system, the backbone component determines the effective development (self-development) of the personality. It can be diagnosed and, consequently, influence these processes. The problem of educating emotional and volitional qualities is especially relevant today, since modern society relies on an independent and proactive person in solving various problems, including life, education, production [4, 5, 6].

According to the results of studying and summarizing the experience of primary school teachers in the process of teaching schoolchildren to educate their

emotional and volitional qualities, an episodic approach is inherent. For the most part, teachers carry it out intuitively, without deep penetration into the content and methods of educating these personal qualities [7, 18].

Therefore, we see the objective expediency of studying the specifics of such a process in the context of educating the emotional and volitional qualities of students during their education in the primary grades. After all, the insufficient development of certain aspects of the disturbed scientific problem makes it difficult to practice an integrated approach to the period of education of younger students, not only in the first grade, but throughout the entire school age [8, 9, 10].

Many factors of spontaneous and specially organized content, as well as natural and social factors, influence the development of the child's personality, the upbringing of his emotional and volitional qualities [5, 10, 11]. The current stage of studying this problem, under the influence of these factors of personality development, attracts the attention of scientists and practitioners to the immediate environment in which the child not only lives, but also realizes his personal qualities, being active, interacting with him [12, 13, 14].

The results of the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature show that within the framework of various conceptual approaches to the assessment of the environment, the features of its pedagogization are studied, taking into account age characteristics in its creation in order to organize optimal interaction within the “environment-personality” system [15, 16].

Significant aspects of the pedagogization of the environment, its functions, structure, as well as the specifics of the play activity and communication of children within its framework are being developed by modern uzbek researchers (D. Yu. Turdimurodov, Ya. M. Abdullaev) [21, 22, 23].

According to the results of the analysis of theoretical and experimental studies and the practice of a number of schools, contradictions were revealed between the high requirements for the education of emotional and volitional qualities of children

of primary school age and the level of methodological approaches to the organization of the learning and playing environment at the stage of primary education [24]. With adequately organized work, it would be possible to ensure the development of the emotional and volitional qualities of a person that are relevant in the modern world. The purpose of the study was the theoretical substantiation of the expediency of using the educational-playing environment for the development of emotional and volitional qualities in physical education lessons among elementary school students. To achieve the goals set, a theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature data were used.

The correct organization of the learning and playing environment has a significant impact on the effectiveness of teaching younger students. In the study we have begun, we consider it expedient to model a variant of the learning-playing environment based on established ideas about its functions and the results of scientific research. We consider the learning and gaming environment as a game in content and as an educational goal (the division is conditional within the framework of the concept of developmental education).

The model of the learning-playing environment was built according to the block principle. Therefore, it includes theoretical-methodological, psychological-pedagogical and technological blocks that interact in a subordinate manner, so that they are functionally interconnected. The theoretical and methodological block of the developed model, it is advisable to create it at the stage of initial education, reveals the initial theoretical provisions (the basis of the modeled object), represents its main components. We consider the theoretical and methodological block as the basis for other blocks of the model.

In defining the goal, we proceed from the essence of the learning and gaming environment as a kind of developing environment. So, we mean the environment that contributes to the versatile development of the personality, the education of its emotional and volitional qualities. Accordingly, the overall goal of creating and

using a learning and playing environment in teaching younger students is to educate the emotional and volitional qualities of each student in learning, subject to interaction with the components of the learning and playing environment, which allows you to create conditions for awareness and intensive learning, providing psychological comfort for each student in learning.

The purpose of the educational-playing environment - the education of emotional and volitional qualities - is considered as a system-creating factor, so that when creating a model, all its components are focused on educating the emotional and volitional qualities of children of primary school age.

Based on the content of the theoretical and methodological block, the psychological and pedagogical block of the model reflects the initial principles tangent to it, which are the basis of the learning and playing environment in the conditions of primary education for schoolchildren, the structure of its organization, as well as the forms of its functioning.

The technological block of the model reflects the structure of the organization of the learning and playing environment in a particular lesson, which reveals the stages of this process within the lesson, determines the structure of the organization of learning in the conditions of the learning and playing environment, predicts methods and means, informing the teacher about the dynamics of the development of emotional and volitional qualities of students . Demonstrates how the pedagogical regulation of the upbringing of the emotional and volitional qualities of students in the classroom occurs when they interact with the learning and gaming environment. In the structure of interaction with the learning and playing environment, not only the sequence and formal combination of stages is essential, but also the features of setting and achieving the goal of the learning and playing environment at each stage. It is important to take into account that the method of goal-setting, provided by the technology of the approach, is characterized by increased instrumentality. In the content of interaction with the learning-game environment within the lesson, we

distinguish invariant (common for all types of lessons-games) and variable (reflection of the specifics of the manifestation of the invariant part for a certain type of lessons-games) substructures.

To study the dynamics of educating the emotional and volitional qualities of students in a learning and playing environment, at each stage it was considered necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the learning and playing environment as a factor in educating emotional and volitional qualities. So, we analyzed in stages the changes in the main components of the structure of emotional-volitional qualities, their interrelations, levels of development, difficulties in their course. The results of current observations were included in the regulatory pedagogical activity for the organization of learning in a learning-play environment (in the operational regulation and design of the development of emotional and volitional qualities).

Conclusions. The model of the learning and playing environment, built on the block principle, includes three mutually subordinate and interdependent blocks: theoretical and methodological, psychological and pedagogical, and technological. We consider the learning-play environment as a real, complex, open, dynamic system with purposeful guidance, and also as an evolving one.

In the study that has begun, in addition to modeling the learning-playing environment, the priority tasks include the justification of the technology for organizing the education of primary school students in this environment, in order to educate emotional and volitional qualities.

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